

EXCELERATE Deliverable D13.3

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2. Executive Summary

ELIXIR's International Strategy describes current activities of international relevance, and planned implementation actions to reinforce ELIXIR's global significance and impact. An update is released on an annual basis. In the context of this document, the term 'International' means 'beyond Europe', with 'Europe' defined as the countries of the European Research Area¹ (ERA).

The Strategy is articulated around four main objectives: *(1) scale-up the international user base of ELIXIR's Services, (2) improve bioinformatics services and promote global standards, (3) expand Membership in ELIXIR beyond Europe, and (4) ensure that ELIXIR is recognised as an infrastructure of global relevance, and a partner of choice by intergovernmental organisations.*

The international audience of the Strategy encompasses users of bioinformatics services, national-level bioinformatics infrastructures, and government officials in Ministries. Also targeted by this Strategy are international bioinformatics-related initiatives[□] and organisations, and intergovernmental organisations. Closer to home, the Strategy aims to raise awareness of ELIXIR's global significance within Member countries, and guide efforts to ensure coherent implementation actions in support of the objectives of the Strategy.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/era/eraprogress_en.htm

The strategy will be implemented through a concrete set of Actions, described in Annex I, each relating to one of the four specific Objectives.

3. Impact

ELIXIR first launched its International Strategy in 2016, and provided an update in 2017. To date, there has been almost 400 visits to the permanent home page (and related pages) of the Strategy on the ELIXIR website². Looking forwards, the 2018 version of the Strategy (presented in this Deliverable) is proposing a number of draft indicators (see Annex II) to assess progress against objectives. Of note, the ELIXIR activities presented in the 2018 version of the Strategy are, for the first time, articulated around UN Sustainable Development Goals³, thereby highlighting how ELIXIR contributes to tackling global challenges.

Highlights of ELIXIR's presence on the global stage can be found in section “*An international perspective of ELIXIR*” of the Strategy. Further, the news item⁴ produced to coincide with the release of the 2018 version of the Strategy lists some of the achievements that took place since the release of the previous version of the Strategy (Autumn 2017).

4. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Deliver world-leading data services for academia and industry: Stimulate innovation by supporting industry uptake of ELIXIR resources, particularly in SMEs.	✓	
2	Complete the management and organisational processes for an efficient distributed infrastructure: Develop and implement an ELIXIR-wide Communications strategy that will engage users and disseminate project outcomes to user communities	✓	

5. Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes • No

² <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/collaborations/international-strategy>

³ <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>

⁴ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/news/international-strategy>

6. Adjustments made

This report was delayed to September 2018 to coincide with the annual launch of the International Strategy at the *International Conference on Research Infrastructure* (ICRI, 12-14 September 2018, Vienna, Austria, <https://www.icri2018.at>), thereby ensuring maximum visibility with funders and policy-makers.

7. Background information

Background information on this Work Package (WP) as originally indicated in the description of action (DoA) is included here for reference.

Work package number	13	Start date or starting event:	month 1
Work package title	Communications, Industry and Community Engagement		
Lead	Andrew Smith (ELIXIR Hub)		
Participant number and person months per participant			
1 – EMBL 36PM			
Objectives			
<p>The overall aim of WP13 is to ensure that a maximum number of scientists and companies are aware of ELIXIR's services, developments, opportunities and events. Reaching out to specific communities, including industry and SMEs, will allow ELIXIR to understand user's needs better, ensuring that the most effective services are developed. This will be achieved by carrying out tasks that address four, complementary objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a coordinated and user-centric Communications presence for ELIXIR. (Task 13.1) • Support innovation and usage of ELIXIR from Europe's life-science industries and SMEs. (Task 13.2) • Create specific outreach channels to key user communities. (Task 13.3) • Engage potential members across the globe. (Task 13.4) <p>WP13 will build upon many existing communications resources and channels. The main ELIXIR-Europe website, for example, will house the project website and existing ELIXIR stakeholder mailing lists will help ensure that outcomes from the project are disseminated widely. WP13 will focus on enhancing these existing platforms and optimising them to ensure maximum impact from a relatively modest WP budget.</p>			
Work Package Lead: Andrew Smith (ELIXIR Hub)			
Description of work and role of partners			

WP13 - Communications, Industry and Community Engagement [Months: 1-48]**EMBL**

It is estimated by the EC that there are around 500,000 life scientists in the EU alone. The fundamental importance of data-driven research in the life sciences means that many of these scientists are potential users of ELIXIR's services. ELIXIR likely has largest user community of any ESFRI Research Infrastructure. Furthermore, ELIXIR's Preparatory Phase report highlighted the range of users supported, including: bioinformaticians and computational biologists; bench scientists; biologists; geneticists; biochemists; clinical specialists; and plant, environmental and marine scientists. In addition, industry is a major user of ELIXIR resources from Pharmaceutical and Biotech industries through to crop science and aquaculture companies and SMEs.

Unlike many physical or single-sited infrastructures, where operators can build face to face dialogue with a small number of users, ELIXIR is an Open Data infrastructure where millions users access services via web interfaces. It is vital to create the effective communications and outreach mechanisms to interact with these users in a manner that is effective for users and efficient for ELIXIR partners.

Task 13.1: Develop a coordinated and user-centric Communications presence for ELIXIR (16PM)

The scale of users across the globe requires that ELIXIR uses modern, effective tools to communicate its scientific and operational messages. The distributed nature of ELIXIR, with over 100 institutes involved, also requires that there is a consistency and clarity of messaging between partners. Task 1 comprises three Sub-tasks that will collectively ensure that the internal processes are in place so that ELIXIR can present a single, coordinated interface to its users and that effective communications materials are developed.

Partners: EMBL-ELIXIR

Subtask 13.1.1: Develop and implement an ELIXIR-wide Communications Strategy (8PM)

The ELIXIR Communications Strategy will set the overall strategic direction for ELIXIR's dissemination activities to users in academia, industry policy-makers and funders. The strategy will include scientific communication, social media, web-based resources, newsletters, video and printed materials. It will be reviewed and updated annually to take into account new technologies and developments. Owned by the ELIXIR Hub, it will be developed jointly by the emerging Communication Expert group (Task 13.1.2) and other key strategic bodies, most notably the ELIXIR Heads of Nodes committee and the Work Package leads of ELIXIR-EXCELERATE. It will identify the key scientific conferences that ELIXIR should attend and the suite of materials that will be produced to reach out to user groups (Task 13.1.3). It will also harness the existing social media channels run by ELIXIR Nodes, and build on the distribution channels created during ELIXIR's Preparatory and interim phases.

Subtask 13.1.2: Create and operate an ELIXIR Communications Expert group (4PM)

In order to implement the most effective Communications Strategy, a tightly-coordinated network of communications and outreach experts from ELIXIR Nodes is required. Harnessing the local communication channels that ELIXIR Nodes already have with their own respective national bioinformatics communities will provide efficiencies of scale at the

European-level. We will create an information exchange network of Node experts that adopts the latest software and web-based applications. Annual face-to-face meetings of all Communications experts and bilateral meetings between members will be critical to cement relationships within the network, and will be supplemented by video/telephone conferencing and use of the ELIXIR intranet (WP12).

Subtask 13.1.3 Develop suite of high-quality communications materials (4PM)

To effectively communicate ELIXIR's services to various stakeholder communities, a suite of high-quality promotional materials will be produced. A short ELIXIR video will feature interviews with scientists and industry users and will set out the structure of ELIXIR, the range of services offered and how these can be accessed. Printed materials, posters and banners will be printed and distributed to all ELIXIR Nodes to support their local dissemination activities. Annual scientific reports will capture the scientific and operational output of ELIXIR- EXCELERATE.

Additional resources required: Video and printed materials subcontracting costs €45,000

Task 13.2: Support innovation and usage of ELIXIR by Europe's life-science industries and SMEs (8PM)

Industrial use of Europe's bioinformatics resources is high. These industries are major employers globally, generating wealth and supporting transformation to a knowledge-based economy. Industry sees added value in ELIXIR in terms of reduced costs and decreased duplication of effort for them, higher scalability, access to common data and interface standards and much better public-private data integration. Many of these requirements will be addressed by the general implementation of ELIXIR and are as relevant for academia as for industry. Additionally, Task 13.2 will ensure that industry and SMEs are offered direct, bespoke support and engagement.

Subtask 13.2.1: Build lasting partnerships with industry initiatives, bodies and SME associations (4PM)

In order to understand the needs of Europe's industry and SME sector, it is necessary to forge close links with industry and SME association bodies, particularly EFPIA, local EENs, the European Biotechnology Network, the BioBasedIndustries Consortium and regional bioclusters. A scoping exercise and face-to-face meetings will map these organisations and establish dissemination channels. This will ensure that a maximum number of companies are aware of ELIXIR's services and that the content of ELIXIR's Innovation and SME programme (Task 13.2.2) is relevant to the needs of Europe's SMEs. The Innovative Medicine Initiative (IMI) - and many of its current projects - is considered as a priority for closer engagement. ELIXIR will seek to conclude formal collaboration agreements with key IMI projects such as OpenPHACTS.

Subtask 13.2.2: Expand the reach and impact of ELIXIR's Innovation and SME programme (4PM)

Expanding ELIXIR's emerging Innovation and SME programme will allow partners to disseminate the results, services, tools and outcomes to a large number of companies across Europe. Building on a successful start to this programme, we will fund 8 dedicated events across the duration of the project. With around 50 delegates attending each event,

hundreds of Europe's SMEs will be directly supported across the duration of the grant. Individual events will be themed to address the outcomes from ELIXIR-EXCELERATE Use Cases (WPs 6 to 9) so will include health and rare diseases, marine sciences and plant sciences. We will work through the key bioclusters and industry organisations identified within Task 13.2.1.

Additional resources required: €120,000 for Innovation and SME events (€15,000 per event)

Task 13.3: Create specific outreach channels across the globe to key user communities and potential member states (6PM)

No infrastructure is effective over the long-term unless it offers services that meet the needs of users. The Preparatory Phase showed that ELIXIR is perhaps unique in the size and variety of its respective user communities. Task 13.3.1 will ensure that ELIXIR engages effectively with users through attendance at scientific conferences. Task and 13.3.2 will allow ELIXIR to forge lasting relations with the key bioinformatics community-driven initiatives such as GOBLET for training and proteomics standards initiatives. In addition, for ELIXIR to realise its potential on the world stage and drive global bioinformatics collaboration, regular interaction, and ultimately direct membership from countries outside Europe, is required. Equally, collaboration with other major global data initiatives is necessary. Task 13.3.3 will ensure that ELIXIR works strategically with key countries outside Europe and the major international infrastructure initiatives that are of relevance.

Subtask 13.3.1. ELIXIR representation at key scientific events and conferences (3PM)

Scientific conferences provide an effective way of communicating ELIXIR's services to its large and diverse user base. ELIXIR will attend, display booths and run tech track sessions at a number of key scientific conferences within Europe and beyond. Conference participation will focus primarily on showcasing ELIXIR to scientific conferences at which ELIXIR's users attend. However, some conferences will have policy-makers and funders as the target audience. The exact conferences to attend will be defined in the ELIXIR Communication's Strategy but major events are summarised in Part B section 2.2.5.

Additional resources required: Conference costs of €40,000

Subtask 13.3.2: Forge lasting relations with bioinformatics community initiatives (3PM)

In the life sciences, many users, developers and operators that share a common interest are organised into 'communities'. Many of these are very well established taking the form of initiatives, networks, societies or consortia. I.e. the "HUPO Proteomics Standards Initiative" for the development of standards in proteomics. Such communities provide fora for knowledge exchange and collaboration and platforms for driving common agreements and community development. ELIXIR recognises the contribution of these and will interact with them strategically. We will not duplicate their efforts but rather engage with them to support and promote their, adding value at the European level. This Task will ensure that ELIXIR identifies and collaborates with the key initiatives.

Task 13.4: Develop ELIXIR's International strategy (6PM)

ELIXIR is considered by the G20 countries to be of global significance and with great potential for membership by countries outside of Europe. Task 13.4 will facilitate the process of countries joining ELIXIR as members, thus addressing the Call requirement of increasing membership. The International Strategy will have a two-fold purpose: 1) support the membership of countries outside of Europe, particularly G20 countries; 2) and foster collaboration between ELIXIR and global science initiatives, such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health and the International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility. The International Strategy will primarily serve as an internal document and will be subject to annual updates following review by ELIXIR Board and the Scientific Advisory Board.

8. Appendix 1: Report on ELIXIR's International Strategy

Introduction

ELIXIR first launched its International Strategy in 2016, and provided an update in 2017⁵. As part of the annual updating of this document (a current requirement under the EXCELERATE grant), this Deliverable represents a significant update to the Strategy.

The International Strategy presented here is an illustrated, high-level and externally-facing document that aims to place ELIXIR in an international context, and for a non-specialist audience. It indeed assumes no prior knowledge of ELIXIR, nor of the important role played by research infrastructures in support of tackling global challenges such as the UN Sustainable Goals.

The main changes in the 2018 version of the Strategy are:

- An “About this Strategy” section replaces the executive summary;
- The previous four strategic objectives have been refined to describe ‘what the Strategy wishes to achieve’, rather than “what ELIXIR will do”, with key target stakeholder groups identified;
- The Strategy has been restructured around ‘thematic areas’, for the benefit of the reader who might not be familiar with ELIXIR’s work, particularly how this research infrastructure is organised around ELIXIR *Platforms* and *Communities*;
- There are two entirely new sections relating to: (1) the implementation of the Strategy (see concrete actions in Annex I), and (2) how progress against Strategic Objectives could be measured (see draft indicators in Annex II).

This following two sections present:

- the *International Strategy* (2018 version), including its unpublished Annex II (*What will success look like?*), and
- what actions have been taken to disseminate it to key stakeholders.

⁵ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B8in1NtGRloYTDhHTIVTWnZUNTg/view>

ELIXIR's International Strategy

The full-resolution document can be downloaded in PDF format at:

<https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/collaborations/international-strategy>. Screenshots of its contents are presented below.

ELIXIR

International Strategy

September 2018

About this Strategy

This Strategy describes the current ELIXIR activities of international relevance, and planned implementation actions to reinforce ELIXIR's global significance and impact. An update is released on an annual basis¹. In the context of this document, the term 'International' means 'beyond Europe', with 'Europe' defined as the countries of the European Research Area (ERA)².

The Strategy is articulated around four main objectives:

1. Scale-up the international user base of ELIXIR's Services
2. Improve bioinformatics services and promote global standards
3. Expand Membership in ELIXIR beyond Europe, and
4. Ensure that ELIXIR is recognised as an infrastructure of global relevance, and a partner of choice by intergovernmental organisations

The international audience of the Strategy encompasses users of bioinformatics services, national-level bioinformatics infrastructures, and government officials in Ministries. Also targeted by this Strategy are international bioinformatics-related initiatives and organisations, and intergovernmental organisations. Closer to home, the Strategy aims to raise awareness of ELIXIR's global significance within Member countries, and guide efforts to ensure coherent implementation actions in support of the objectives of the Strategy.

The strategy will be implemented through a concrete set of Actions, described in Annex I, each relating to one of the four specific Objectives.

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On the importance of research infrastructures for life science data

Modern life science research is data-intensive. Further, these data are very heterogeneous in scope, from genetic sequence and their expression to proteins, and then observable characteristics. Research infrastructures underpin access to life science data and the various services derived from them. These infrastructures are critical to bioinformatics research and its many applications in the fields of health (e.g. personalised medicine), food security (e.g. aquaculture) and the environment (e.g. pollution), which are of significant societal and economic benefits. Together, life science research infrastructures and bioinformatics research are important pillars supporting 150+ countries in their efforts to reach some of the UN Sustainable Development Goals they have collectively committed to (Figure 1).³

ELIXIR is Europe's research infrastructure for life sciences data

ELIXIR unites Europe's leading life science organisations in managing and safeguarding the increasing volume of data being generated by publicly funded research. ELIXIR coordinates, integrates and sustains bioinformatics resources across its country

Nodes, and enables users in academia and industry, wherever they are based on the planet, to freely access services that are vital for their work.

ELIXIR is an intergovernmental organisation of 21 Member Countries, 1 Observer country, plus the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) (Figure 2). It is a distributed infrastructure, with a Hub acting as the coordination secretariat, and Nodes in each of the Member countries, plus the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), itself a Node.

International perspective of ELIXIR

Bioinformatics is a global science, as evidenced by the geographic location of its data producers, service providers, and users. ELIXIR's Services⁴ have a truly global user base. In the first seven months of 2018, there were almost 50,000 users of the ELIXIR website (www.elixir-europe.org), of which 21,500 were located beyond Europe (including 7,500 in North America alone, the remainder elsewhere on the globe). Orphanet, the international rare disease and orphan drug database, has around 782,000 visitors per month from most countries on the globe⁵. Moreover, a number of other ELIXIR Services, such as UniProt⁶ (a database on protein sequence and functional information), are run as part of international (i.e. beyond Europe) collaborations and funding arrangements.⁷

ELIXIR has established formal agreements with

Figure 1. Life science research infrastructures and bioinformatics research are important pillars supporting 150+ countries in their efforts to reach some of the UN Sustainable Development Goals they have collectively committed to: Goal 2 Zero Hunger; Goal 3 Good Health and Wellbeing; Goal 9 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure; Goal 14 Life Below Water; and Goal 15 Life on Land

international bioinformatics-related initiatives⁸. For instance, it collaborates with the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) in developing and promoting standards and frameworks for the responsible sharing and reuse of genomics data⁹. Finally, in the policy sphere, ELIXIR is recognised as a Research Infrastructure of Global Interest by the Group of Senior Officials of the G7¹⁰, whilst the Swiss Node (SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics) is a "Reference Centre"¹¹ for bioinformatics of the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, in the context of a collaboration in relation to zoonotic and animal diseases.

Objectives of the International Strategy

This Strategy supports ELIXIR's vision of standards-based and well-annotated life-science data that are internationally shared and accessed. It also aims to support the long-term sustainability of ELIXIR's Services, by demonstrating to its funders (e.g. national governments, the European Union) that continued investment in ELIXIR Nodes leads to scientific and socio-economic impact. The objectives of the Strategy, and the stakeholder groups they target, can be found in Table 1.

Figure 2. ELIXIR Members by their year of accession. ELIXIR is an inter-governmental organisation of 21 Member Countries, 1 Observer, plus the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL). Although the current membership of ELIXIR is focused on European countries, its legal framework allows for membership of non European countries.

Table 1. Objectives of the International Strategy, and the stakeholders they target.

	Strategic objectives	Target stakeholder(s)
	1. Scale-up the international user base of ELIXIR's Services	Users of ELIXIR's Services in countries beyond Europe
	2a Improve bioinformatics services and promote global standards through formal/concrete collaborations with...	...national-level bioinformatics service providers in countries beyond Europe (in support of Objective 3)
	2b	...international bioinformatics-related initiatives and organisations (e.g. the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health)
	3 Expand Membership in ELIXIR beyond Europe	Government officials in Ministries of countries beyond Europe, with support from the country's bioinformatics community (outcome of Objective 2b)
	4 Ensure that ELIXIR is recognised as an infrastructure of global relevance, and a partner of choice by intergovernmental organisations	Intergovernmental organisations, including policy-makers, (e.g. the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations)

Key Organisations, Initiatives and Projects

The following section of the International Strategy lists the key international organisations, initiatives and projects and their relevant counterpart in ELIXIR (see 'Focal point in ELIXIR column'). For the benefit of those not as familiar with ELIXIR, and to allow for readers to identify quickly the areas they are likely to be interested in, it is divided into a series of tables: Core infrastructure, Health, Food security, Environment, Research infrastructure policy, and Relations with countries beyond Europe.

Core infrastructure

The activities of ELIXIR's Scientific Programme³² are carried out within five 'Platforms'. These are: Data, Tools, Interoperability, Compute and Training.³³ Table 2 below lists the 'international' (i.e. beyond Europe) organisations, initiatives and projects with which ELIXIR engages actively as part of the work carried out under its five Platforms and other Use Cases. This engagement helps ensure that synergies are exploited, effort duplication avoided, and ultimately better services are developed for end-users.

Table 2. 'International' (i.e. beyond Europe) organisations, initiatives and projects with which ELIXIR engages actively as part of the work carried out under its five "Platforms" (Data, Tools, Interoperability, Compute and Training) and other Use Cases. Platforms are domains of technical implementation. 'Focal point(s) in ELIXIR' either refers to an existing focal point, or a 'natural fit' in ELIXIR.

Organisation, initiative, or project	Mission, vision, or goals	Purpose of engagement	Focal point(s) in ELIXIR	Main objective
Committee on Data of the International Council for Science (CODATA)	Promote global collaboration to improve the availability and usability of data for all areas of research	Contribute to global discussions on data resources, access to tool and services, and sustainability of global initiatives. Run joint events, develop curriculum and training materials in collaboration with CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Schools. ³⁴	Interoperability, Compute and Tools Platforms, Marine Metagenomics Use Case,	
Common Workflow Language	Enabling the reuse, extension, scaling, and reproducibility of scientific workflows	Support collective efforts around global interoperability of workflows and tools, promote key cloud enabling technologies including AAI (Authorization and Authentication Infrastructure), Task and Workflow Execution Services	Marine Metagenomics Use Case, Compute Platform, Tools Platform	
CyVerse	Design, deploy, and expand a national Cyberinfrastructure for Life Sciences research, and to train scientists in its use	Ensure mutual awareness of activities	Hub, ELIXIR UK	
Galaxy	A platform for data intensive biomedical research	Via the ELIXIR Galaxy Community ³⁵ , make it easier to import data into Galaxy instances, help develop and share Galaxy tools and workflows, provision container instances on cloud compute and increase the provision of Galaxy training	Tools Platform, Training Platform, Compute Platform, ELIXIR Communities	
Global Life Sciences Data Resources Coalition³⁶	Towards coordinated international support of core data resources for the life science	Contribute to collective efforts to ensure the long-term sustainability of core data resources, notably via identifying a host organisation for the coordination efforts and awareness raising with HIRO .	Data Platform	
GOBLET (Global Organisation for Bioinformatics Learning, Education and Training)	Unite, inspire and equip bioinformatics trainers worldwide	Take forwards a training strategy ³⁷ to support complementary activities between GOBLET and ELIXIR, thereby strengthening international training links	Training Platform	
Human Proteome Organisation (HUPO) Proteomics Standards Initiative (PSI)	Define community standards for data representation in proteomics to facilitate data comparison, exchange and verification	Take forwards a training strategy to support complementary activities between GOBLET and ELIXIR, thereby strengthening international training links. Assure implementation of HUPO standards across the ELIXIR Proteomics Community and input into standards development	Proteomics community, EMBL-EBI	

Organisation, initiative, or project	Mission, vision, or goals	Purpose of engagement	Focal point(s) in ELIXIR	Main objective
Metabolomics Society	Promote the growth, use and understanding of metabolomics in the life sciences	Ensure mutual awareness of activities, promote and develop open standards for data reporting	ELIXIR UK, Metabolomics Community, Data Platform, Interoperability Platform, Tools Platform	
Research Data Alliance (RDA)	Research data sharing without barriers	Support collective efforts towards the global interoperability of data, notably via the ELIXIR Bridging Force Interest Group ¹⁸ and the FAIRsharing (previously BioSharing) Working Group ¹⁹ . Run joint events, develop curriculum and training materials in collaboration with CO-DATA-RDA Research Data Science Schools ²⁰	All ELIXIR Platforms	
schema.org	Create, maintain, and promote schemas for structured data on the Internet	Support collective efforts around data repository descriptions, and data findability and accessibility, for instance via bioschemas.org	Interoperability Platform, Data Platform, all ELIXIR Use Cases	
The Carpentries	Teach foundational coding and data science skills to researchers worldwide	Run joint workshops on Software Carpentry and Data Carpentry Foundations, train instructors and continue developing training materials ²¹	Training Platform	

Health

Applications of bioinformatics in the health sector are well recognised, ranging from disease diagnostic (e.g. rare diseases) and prevention (e.g. certain cancers), to personalised medicine (or precision medicine), and the development of new treatments. Table 3 lists international organisations, initiatives and projects in the health sector with which ELIXIR engages.

Table 3. International (i.e. beyond Europe) organisations, initiatives and projects in the health sector with which ELIXIR engages. "Focal point(s) in ELIXIR" either refers to an existing focal point, or a 'natural fit' in ELIXIR.

Organisation, initiative, or project	Mission, vision, or goals	Purpose of engagement	Focal point(s) in ELIXIR	Main objective
Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)	Enabling responsible genomic data sharing for the benefit of human health	Support global efforts towards better collaboration on human sensitive data, notably via standard development (e.g. ELIXIR Beacon ²² Driver Project, Cloud Workstream and Authorization and Authentication Infrastructure), working groups, event sponsorship	Human Data Use Case, Compute Platform, Interoperability Platform, Tools Platform	

Organisation, initiative, or project	Mission, vision, or goals	Purpose of engagement	Focal point(s) in ELIXIR	Main objective
Human Cell Atlas	Enabling the reuse, extension, scaling, and reproducibility of scientific workflows	Ensure mutual awareness of activities	Marine Metagenomics Use Case, Compute Platform, Tools Platform	
International Rare Diseases Research Consortium (IRDIRC)	Enable all people living with a rare disease to receive an accurate diagnosis, care, and available therapy within one year of coming to medical attention	Collaborate on common outreach and communication activities, e.g. during innovation events, coordinated through the Orphanet ²³ resource and the RD-Connect platform ²⁴	Rare Diseases Use Case	
RD-Connect	Facilitate research on rare diseases by connecting databases, patient registries, biobanks and clinical bioinformatics data into a central resource for researchers worldwide	Link ELIXIR tools, service and expertise to the RD-Connect platform ²⁵	Human Data Use Case, Data Platform, Interoperability Platform	

Food security

Successful applications of bioinformatics to food production can be found in agriculture, farming and aquaculture, and are key to ensuring security of food supplies globally. In particular, resistance to pests and pathogens has been shown to help reduce the cost of food production. Table 4 lists international organisations, initiatives and projects of relevance to food security and with which ELIXIR and its Nodes engage.

Table 4. International (i.e. beyond Europe) organisations, initiatives and projects of relevance to food security and with which ELIXIR and its Nodes engage. "Focal point(s) in ELIXIR" either refers to an existing focal point, or to a 'natural fit' in ELIXIR.

Organisation, initiative, or project	Mission, vision, or goals	Purpose of engagement	Focal point(s) in ELIXIR	Main objective
Breeding API (BrAPI)	Enable interoperability among plant databases used for breeding and plant environment studies for climate change adaptation	Collaborate on the development and adoption of the Breeding API (Application Programming Interface)	Plant Science Use Case, ELIXIR France, ELIXIR Netherlands	

Organisation, initiative, or project	Mission, vision, or goals	Purpose of engagement	Focal point(s) in ELIXIR	Main objective
DivSeek	Unlock the potential of crop diversity so that it can be utilised to enhance the productivity, sustainability and resilience of crops and agricultural systems	Ensure alignment of ELIXIR and DivSeek's activities around crop diversity	Plant Sciences Use Case	
Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations	Achieve food security for all and make sure that people have regular access to enough high-quality food to lead active, healthy lives	Be a "Reference Centre" in bioinformatics of the FAO for the screening, monitoring and follow-up of zoonotic diseases (or zoonoses), and for animal diseases	ELIXIR Switzerland ²⁶	
Global Open Data for Agriculture and Nutrition (goDAN)	Promote the proactive sharing of open data to make information about agriculture and nutrition available, accessible and usable	Carry out outreach and communication activities	ELIXIR Netherlands	
International Plant Phenotyping Network (IPPN)	Support the exploitation of crop genetic diversity, plant traits and the analysis of genotype performance in current and future agro-climatic scenarios	Collaborate on systems and services development and collaborate on data standards development, in particular MIAPPE ²⁷ . This is conducted in direct collaboration with the European plant phenotyping infrastructure (Emphasis ²⁸) which belongs to IPPN	Plant Science Use Case, ELIXIR France, ELIXIR Belgium	
International Wheat Information System (WheatIS)	Support the wheat research community by building an International Wheat Information System	Collaborate on systems and services development	ELIXIR France	

Environment

The environment, including biodiversity and ecosystem services, is probably the area where bioinformatics applications have the greatest unrealised potential to date. Bioinformatics can, for instance, provide solutions for pollution control and remediation, whilst metagenomics is about to revolutionise our biogeographic knowledge of species and habitats, having already provided hope for the development of new antibiotics. Table 5 lists international organisations and initiatives of relevance to the environment and with which ELIXIR engages.

Table 5. International (i.e. beyond Europe) organisations and initiatives of relevance to the environment and with which ELIXIR engages. "Focal point(s) in ELIXIR" either refers to an existing focal point, or to a 'natural fit' in ELIXIR.

Organisation, initiative, or project	Mission, vision, or goals	Purpose of engagement	Focal point(s) in ELIXIR	Main objective
Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)	Provide anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth	Enrich species occurrence data and the GBIF taxonomy with information derived from genetic sequences	Hub, Plant Sciences Use Case, Marine Metagenomics Use Case	
Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO BON)	Improve the acquisition, coordination and delivery of biodiversity observations and related services to users including decision makers and the scientific community	Scope possible synergies with the activities of the emerging 'Genetics Working Group' and GLOMICON (Global Omics Observatory Network)	Hub, EMBL-EBI, Interoperability Platform	
Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS)	Facilitate free and open access to, and application of, biodiversity and biogeographic data and information on marine life	Enrich species occurrence data with information derived from genetic sequences	Hub, Marine Metagenomics Use Case	

Research infrastructure policy

Research infrastructures are sustained via public investments. This is particularly true in the life sciences where services from these infrastructures are typically free to users, based on open data policies and open software licenses. It is hence in the countries' interest to work together and ensure that good practices are shared, 'internationalisation'²⁹ opportunities identified, and impact is demonstrated. Table 6 lists intergovernmental organisations with which ELIXIR engages in relation to global research infrastructure policy.

Table 6. Intergovernmental organisations with which ELIXIR engages in relation to global research infrastructure policy.

Organisation, initiative, or project	Mission, vision, or goals	Purpose of engagement	Focal point(s) in ELIXIR	Main objective
G7's Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on global Research Infrastructures	Explore cooperation opportunities in Global Research Infrastructures	Continue to be a partner of choice in GSO activities related to research infrastructure, for instance sharing good practices, and identifying internationalisation opportunities. Facilitate ELIXIR Membership of G20 countries beyond Europe	Hub	
Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)	Promote policies that will improve the economic and social well-being of people around the world	Continue to be a visible partner of choice in OECD activities related to Research Infrastructure Policy ³⁹ , notably sustainability, socio-economic impact and the internationalisation of databases	Hub	

Relations with countries beyond Europe

Expanding ELIXIR's Membership³¹ beyond Europe is an effective way of raising ELIXIR's international profile and impact. Although the current membership of ELIXIR is very much focused on European countries, its legal framework, the 'ELIXIR Consortium Agreement'³², allows for membership of non European countries. Membership, however, is not always the end target, and significant mutual benefits can be achieved before membership negotiations are considered or even relevant.

Although proceeding towards ELIXIR Membership is ultimately the decision of a national government³³, it usually is the result of interest shown by the national bioinformatics community. Benefits of ELIXIR Membership include enhancing national-level bioinformatics services through linkages across borders, and training at the national-level. These benefits help increase the scientific, technological and socio-economic impacts, and hence added-value, of national-level investments in bioinformatics.

Where relevant and desired, ELIXIR will work towards expanding Membership beyond Europe, acknowledging that this process can take years. In other cases, ELIXIR will develop formal/concrete collaborations with national-level bioinformatics infrastructures, for mutual benefit. See Table 7 for a selection.

Table 7. Selection of countries with which ELIXIR has emerging or existing dialogue, formal/concrete collaboration(s) or potential interest in Membership.

Country	Status or aim of engagement	Focal point(s) in ELIXIR	Focal entity, project, initiative, at country-level	Main objective
Australia	Supporting future path towards membership	Hub	EMBL Australia Bioinformatics Resource (EMBL-ABR), Melbourne Bioinformatics ³⁴ , Bioplatforms Australia; Country Delegation to G7's Group of Senior Officials	
Canada	Supporting future path towards membership	Hub, Human Data Use Case, Nodes	Genome Canada , Ontario Institute for Cancer Research (collaboration via the ELIXIR Beacon project), Various ongoing projects (e.g. EC-funded topic on personalised medicine); Country Delegation to G7's Group of Senior Officials	
China	Formal/concrete collaboration(s)	ELIXIR UK and EMBL-EBI	Country Delegation to G7's Group of Senior Officials; Project collaboration with BGI and GigaScience via the CUD-DEL (China-UK Data Dissemination in Metabolomics) project, with MetaboLights (EBI) and ISA tools (ELIXIR UK);	
Japan	Formal/concrete collaboration(s)	Hub, ELIXIR UK	Country Delegation to G7's Group of Senior Officials; National Bioscience Database Center (NBDC) and Database Center for Life Science (DBCLS) in the context of the Biohackathon series; dialogue with European offices of JSPS and AMED .	
India	Emerging dialogue	Hub	Country Delegation to G7's Group of Senior Officials.	
Mexico	Emerging dialogue	Hub	Contact initiated with the Center of Genomic Sciences (National Autonomous University of Mexico)	
New Zealand	Formal/concrete collaboration(s)	Hub	Dialogue with Science attaché at New Zealand Embassy in Brussels ; engagement through the International Bioeconomy Forum	
Russia	Emerging dialogue	Hub	National University of Science and Technology via the Country Delegation to G7's Group of Senior Officials	
Singapore	Formal/concrete collaboration(s)	Hub	Collaboration via the ELIXIR Beacon project with Global Gene Corp	

Country	Status or aim of engagement	Focal point(s) in ELIXIR	Focal entity, project, initiative, at country-level	Main objective
South Africa	Supporting future path towards membership	Hub, Training Platform	Human Heredity and Health in Africa (H3Africa) Initiative ; Pan African Bioinformatics Network for H3Africa (H3ABioNet) ; Country Delegation to G7's Group of Senior Officials	
South Korea	Emerging dialogue	Hub	Korea Basic Science Institute, National Research Facilities & Equipment Center	
USA	Formal/concrete collaboration(s)	Hub, Training Platform, Interoperability Platform, Compute Platform, Data Platform, ELIXIR UK, EMBL-EBI	National Institutes of Health (NIH) collaborations via projects under Big Data to Knowledge (BD2K) (e.g. BioCaddie , CEDAR), and the follow-on Data Commons initiative (e.g. ELIXIR's FAIRsharing) California Digital Library (collaboration on identifiers.org); Broad Institute (collaboration via the ELIXIR Beacon project); Country Delegation to G7's Group of Senior Officials.	

How to get involved

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- Andrew Smith, Head of ELIXIR External Relations, andrew.smith@elixir-europe.org

Annex I: Actions to implement the Strategy

A number of actions, listed in Table 8, will be carried out, against each of the strategic objectives, to implement the International Strategy. Implementation actions will be reviewed (i.e. updated, refined) regularly, at least once a year in anticipation to the annual release of the Strategy.

Table 8. Actions to implement the International Strategy.

Strategic objective	Implementation actions
1. Scale-up the international user base of ELIXIR's Services	Continue to advertise specialist bioinformatics training to international participants through TeSS ³⁵ , including courses run outside of Europe. Consider creating a travel grant scheme (with eligibility based on Objective 3). Build on, and expand, joint training events with international partners with the appropriate fund/grant schema.
	Facilitate key international participants to attend ELIXIR-run events, such as hackathons, and Platform-organised workshops. Where relevant/possible, offer travel sponsorship.
	Continue to ensure ELIXIR's visibility at international conferences ³⁶ , via special sessions and interactive workshops led/convened by ELIXIR, event sponsorship (incl. booth with promotional materials and encouragement to sign up to the ELIXIR newsletter), and posters and oral presentations by ELIXIR participants.
	Develop approaches to assess the international user base of ELIXIR Services (for example, for ELIXIR Core Data Resources, ELIXIR training, AAI), ideally using spatio-temporal trends in user numbers
	Map and develop outreach channels with regional bioinformatics associations linked to ISCB (International Society for Computational Biology) ³⁷ .
2a. Improve bioinformatics services and promote global standards through collaborations with international bioinformatics-related initiatives	Develop new and Implement existing agreements (e.g. Collaboration Strategies) to formalise collaborations between ELIXIR and key international bioinformatics or data initiatives.
	Develop a comprehensive presence for International collaboration on the ELIXIR website.
	Work within the Global Life Sciences Data Resources Coalition to establish an international scheme for long-term equitable funding and life-cycle management of key biological data resources.
	Through the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health, promote the implementation of ELIXIR's Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) and Cloud ELIXIR compute technologies as Driver Projects, complementing Beacons as an existing Driver Project.

Strategic objective	Implementation actions
2b. Improve bioinformatics services and promote global standards through collaborations with national-level bioinformatics infrastructures	<p>Encourage the exchange of best practices by extending the existing ELIXIR Staff Exchange Programme³⁸ to allow ELIXIR Node staff to be hosted by service providers located beyond Europe, and conversely, allow international participants to be hosted by an ELIXIR Node if there is clear benefit to ELIXIR. Reciprocal staff exchange arrangements could be considered, with the international partner paying for the cost of hosting their staff within an ELIXIR Node. Funding could also come from applications, supported by the Hub (support letters, matchmaking), to the Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) scheme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions.</p> <p>Encourage/facilitate international interaction in the growing portfolio of ELIXIR Communities³⁹.</p> <p>Promote the participation of countries outside of the European Union in research projects of relevance to ELIXIR funded by the European Union's Framework Programmes⁴⁰.</p> <p>Support key international collaborators in "lighting" a Beacon⁴¹ and expand ELIXIR's activities on the interoperable federation of access controlled data (e.g. Local EGA⁴²) beyond Europe.</p> <p>Promote the uptake, by countries beyond Europe, of standards which ELIXIR helped develop or is strongly invested in by presenting ELIXIR at global conferences and scientific events.</p>
3. Expand Membership in ELIXIR beyond Europe	<p>Harness the visibility of ELIXIR's inclusion on the G7 GSO roadmap to initiate or continue discussions with scientific leaders and government officials in countries considered for ELIXIR Membership. Hold joint high-level events in these countries and host visits of delegations of officials and scientists from those countries.</p> <p>Ensure ELIXIR presence at relevant international events such as the bi-yearly International Conference on Research Infrastructures (ICRI)⁴³.</p>
4. Ensure that ELIXIR is recognised as an infrastructure of global relevance, and a partner of choice by intergovernmental organisations	<p>Ensure that ELIXIR is visible at major intergovernmental events (policy related, but also technical bodies) related to research infrastructure, health, food security, and environment. Facilitate visibility via e.g. plenary interventions, presentations, booth, mentions in official meeting/policy documents, representation at policy-level expert groups.</p> <p>Identify ELIXIR's unique niche, and bioinformatics relevance, in current intergovernmental processes in the fields of research infrastructure, health (e.g. World Health Organization's Programme of Work), food security (e.g. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations: International Seed Treaty⁴⁴), and environment (e.g. United Nations: Convention on Biological Diversity and the Nagoya Protocol⁴⁵, ongoing international negotiations on the conservation and sustainable use of Biodiversity in areas Beyond National Jurisdiction⁴⁶), and the overarching United Nations Sustainable Development Goals⁴⁷. Communicate this value via appropriate communication media (e.g. policy briefs, infographics).</p>
Of relevance to all objectives	<p>Collate information on internationally-relevant ELIXIR activities and outcomes via existing channels, such as periodic reports under grants, attendance at conference calls linked to ELIXIR Platforms and Communities, ELIXIR Weekly Briefs and Key Contributors Updates.</p>

End notes

- 1 The latest version is available at: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/elixir-international-strategy>
- 2 http://ec.europa.eu/research/era/eraprogress_en.htm
- 3 <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>
- 4 <http://elixir-europe.org/services>
- 5 <https://www.orpha.net/orphacom/cahiers/docs/GB/ActivityReportLeaflet2017.pdf>
- 6 UniProt is a collaboration between EMBL-EBI, SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics and the Protein Information Resource. See list of donors at: <https://www.uniprot.org/help/about>
- 7 <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/collaborations>
- 8 <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/collaborations>
- 9 <https://www.elixir-europe.org/news/elixir-and-ga4gh-agree-collaboration-strategy>
- 10 https://www.bmbf.de/files/151109_G7_Broschere.pdf
- 11 https://www.sib.swiss/images/sib/7-about-us/media/news/sib_fao_press_release_en_20150210.pdf
- 12 <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/what-we-do/elixir-programme-2019-2023>
- 13 <https://www.elixir-europe.org/platforms/data>, <https://www.elixir-europe.org/platforms/tools>, <https://www.elixir-europe.org/platforms/interoperability>, <https://www.elixir-europe.org/platforms/compute>, <https://www.elixir-europe.org/platforms/training>.
- 14 <http://www.codata.org/working-groups/research-data-science-summer-schools>. Research data science is the science of looking after, and using, research data
- 15 <https://www.elixir-europe.org/communities/galaxy>
- 16 Further information: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/news/elixir-among-signatories-call-action-global-coalition-sustainable-core-data-resources> (news item) and <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2017/04/27/110825>
- 17 <https://www.elixir-europe.org/news/elixir-and-goblet-publish-joint-training-strategy>
- 18 <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/collaborations/rda>
- 19 <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/biosharing-registry-connecting-data-policies-standards-data-lifesciences.html>
- 20 <http://www.codata.org/working-groups/research-data-science-summer-schools>. Research data science is the science of looking after, and using, research data.
- 21 <https://www.elixir-europe.org/news/elixir-carpentries-agreement>
- 22 <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/implementation-studies/beacons>
- 23 <https://www.orpha.net/consor/cgi-bin/index.php>
- 24 <https://rd-connect.eu/about-rd-connect/>
- 25 Engagement will also be via the RD-Connect Community Executive Board, where ELIXIR is represented (since August 2018).
- 26 https://www.sib.swiss/images/sib/7-about-us/media/news/sib_fao_press_release_en_20150210.pdf
- 27 Minimum Information About a Plant Phenotyping Experiment: <http://www.miappe.org/>
- 28 <https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/>
- 29 Several countries contributing to building one infrastructure, to use collectively.
- 30 <https://www.innovationpolicyplatform.org/research-infrastructure-policy-oecd-project>
- 31 How countries join ELIXIR and establish a Node: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/how-countries-join>
- 32 https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir_consortium_agreement
- 33 Whilst any country in the world can apply for Membership, the ELIXIR Board will review each application against a set of predefined criteria - these criteria, and the process for countries beyond Europe to join ELIXIR-

IR, are available on request to the Hub.

34 Formerly VLSCI (Victorian Life Sciences Computation Initiative)

35 Via TeSS (an ELIXIR Service), which is an online portal that gathers life science training materials and training courses from across Europe, but also beyond. <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

36 E.g. ISMB/ECCB <https://www.iscb.org/ismbeccb2017> or ISMB <https://www.iscb.org/about-ismb>

37 <https://www.iscb.org/affiliated-groups>

38 Note that this funding scheme typically covers travel and accommodation, and not staff time/salary costs.

39 These are currently called Use Cases (<https://www.elixir-europe.org/use-cases>).

40 A number of international countries are able to take part in research projects under Horizon 2020: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/international-cooperation_en.htm#support-non-eu-countries

41 Beacon is a 'genetic mutation sharing platform', used to share genetic data. <https://beacon-network.org/#>

42 <https://github.com/elixir-europe/human-data-local-ega>

43 <https://www.icrizo18.at/>

44 <http://www.fao.org/plant-treaty/en/>

45 <https://www.cbd.int/abs/about/>; Ad Hoc Technical Expert Group (AHTEG) on Digital Sequence Information on Genetic Resources <https://www.cbd.int/abs/dsi-gr/ahteg.shtml>.

46 <https://www.un.org/bbnj/>

47 In particular: Goal 2 Zero Hunger; Goal 3 Good Health and Wellbeing; Goal 9 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Goals 14 Life Below Water and 15 Life On Land

ELIXIR International Strategy

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www.elixir-europe.org

Annex II. What will success look like?

This annex is not part of the public version of the Strategy. Work will be carried out in months to come to refine the draft indicators.

Progress against each of the strategic objectives will be monitored using indicators (Table 9). Indicators are a well-known and well-used tool in policy circles, where they are used to monitor progress against objectives, for instance as part of the implementation of policy instruments such as Conventions and other Agreements.

The use of indicators to monitor implementation is a new approach under the International Strategy, hence it is likely that the draft indicators will need to be improved/refined. Where the desired indicator is not readily available, a proxy could be used to measure what can realistically and readily be measured, until a more suitable option has been developed. Once indicator methodologies are agreed and in place for each objective, associated targets for given time periods will be decided.

Table 9. Proposed indicators to measure progress against each of the strategic objectives. Where the desired indicator is not readily available, a proxy will be used to measure what can realistically and readily be measured, until a more suitable option has been developed.

Strategic objective	Desired indicator of progress	Proxy indicator of progress
1. Scale-up the international user base of ELIXIR's Services	Positive temporal trend in the number of "international" users of ELIXIR's Services	Positive temporal trend in the number of unique "international" users who access the permanent home page of the Strategy on the ELIXIR website ⁶ . <i>Note: this really measures the Web visibility of the Strategy, as measured via Google Analytics</i>
2b. Improve bioinformatics services and promote global standards through collaborations with national-level bioinformatics infrastructures	Positive temporal trend in the number of "international" countries which use ELIXIR tools and standards in their bioinformatics services	Initiation of ELIXIR's "international" Staff Exchange Programme; positive temporal trends in the number of (1) "international" participants in ELIXIR Communities; (2) "international" countries actively working towards "lighting a Beacon"
2a. Improve bioinformatics services and promote global standards through collaborations with international bioinformatics-related initiatives	Positive temporal trend in the number of agreements to formalise collaborations between ELIXIR and international bioinformatics or data initiatives	N/A
3. Expand Membership in ELIXIR beyond Europe	Positive temporal trend in ELIXIR Membership of countries beyond Europe	N/A
4. Ensure that ELIXIR is recognised as an infrastructure of global	Positive temporal trends in the number of (1) mentions of ELIXIR in	N/A

⁶ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/collaborations/international-strategy>

relevance, and a partner of choice by intergovernmental organisations	official international policy documents; (2) representation at international policy-level expert groups; and (3) formal agreements with relevant intergovernmental bodies	
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Dissemination of the International Strategy

So as to help ensure good visibility of the Strategy on the ELIXIR website (and facilitate future updates), the web presence of the Strategy was refocused on two pages only:

- The permanent “home”⁷ of the Strategy can be navigated to from the ELIXIR home page (*Home page => About Us => Collaborations => International Strategy*). A shorter link⁸ leading to the same place is also available for use in documents;
- There is an automatic feed of the Strategy on the “ELIXIR Publications” page⁹.

To ensure maximum exposure, the 2018 version of the International Strategy was launched during the *International Conference on Research Infrastructure*¹⁰ (ICRI), that took place 12-14 September 2018 in Vienna (Austria). This bi-annual event is attended by policy-makers and funders from various fields. As this iteration was a “paperless” event, the Strategy was distributed to participants in electronic format via 60 ELIXIR-branded “USB” wristbands (see screenshot below).

Two of the 60 ELIXIR-branded “USB” wristbands, used to disseminate the International Strategy to selected participants of the 2018 International Conference on Research Infrastructure (ELIXIR banner in the background):

⁷ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/collaborations/international-strategy>

⁸ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/elixir-international-strategy>

⁹ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/publications>

¹⁰ <https://www.icri2018.at>

Upon plugging the wristbands into a computer, a custom-designed local webpage becomes available, to give access to the International Strategy and related key ELIXIR outputs, along with a video presenting ELIXIR (see screenshots below).

Screenshots of the custom-designed local webpage that becomes available upon plugging the USB wristbands onto a computer:

About ELIXIR

ELIXIR coordinates and develops life science resources across Europe so that researchers can more easily find, analyse and share data, exchange expertise, and implement best practices. This makes it possible for them to gain greater insights into how living organisms work.

ELIXIR International Strategy

ELIXIR's International Strategy maps how ELIXIR engages with different global initiatives and countries. It is aimed at a broad range of stakeholders including: users and communities across the world, global bioinformatics and data initiatives, policy makers and funders, and ELIXIR partners.

[Learn more about the ELIXIR International Strategy](#)

ELIXIR support to industry

Industry is already a large user of public bioinformatics resources. From drug discovery to sustainable manufacturing, industry increasingly relies on safe, secure access to bioinformatics datasets, tools, training and standards in order to develop new products and services.

ELIXIR mapped for the first time how small and medium companies rely on public bioinformatics data for their business. The results are published in the report "Public data resources as a business model for SMEs".

[Read the report in pdf](#)

ELIXIR Annual Report 2017

The ELIXIR Annual Report shows the progress of ELIXIR Platforms, Use Cases and ELIXIR Nodes in meeting the objectives of the current ELIXIR Scientific Programme and introduces the work towards the new Programming cycle (2019-2023).

Building one-to-one interactions with key ICRI participants who were offered a wristband, the International Strategy was mentioned by Andrew Smith during his intervention as part of one of the parallel sessions. The launch was further promoted via a news item¹¹ and social networks (e.g. Twitter¹², LinkedIn¹³) using the respective ELIXIR accounts. Finally, the hyperlink to the Strategy has been added to email signatures and will be shared by email with key stakeholders, such as international focal points in partner organisations and government departments.

¹¹ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/news/international-strategy>
¹² <https://twitter.com/ELIXIREurope/status/1040207992979906561>
¹³ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6446015107871834112>

In the Autumn of 2018, work will resume to implement the Strategy, based on the concrete actions identified and detailed in it (see Annex I), including monitoring progress (see Annex II). Possible updates will be collated, in anticipation to including them in the 2019 version, to be released in the Summer of 2019, before the end of the EXCELERATE project.